

Ordinary Matter and Celestial Objects Interaction with Dark Fabric Matter and Energy

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ABSTRACT: In this work, I shall figure out the general structure of a dark fabric matter, and the direct interactions of the celestial objects, ordinary matter, and ordinary energy with dark fabric matter and energy. Dark Fabric matter and energy is a hidden dimension of the parallel universes, visible Universe, galaxies, Atoms, molecules, ordinary matter, celestial objects, stellar systems, and Planetary systems. The Main Structure of Dark fabric matter consists of the Dark matter particles called Fabriton particles, Dark Matter Strings, and Dark Matter Webs. The dark matter particles are named fabriton particles. Fabriton means Fast actively binding reacting in total objects naturally. Fabriton is a good proposed name for dark matter particles to be recognized among subatomic particles. The mystery of Dark matter and the dark energy could be solved here entirely. Einstein and Newton built clear mathematical equations to describe the nature of gravity, after them many other people worked warmly to resolve the reality of gravity, dark matter, and dark energy. Gravity is the ripples, curvatures, gravitational waves, and tunnels that formed rapidly in the structure of dark fabric matter and energy when celestial objects and ordinary matter particles passed throughout it directly.

KEYWORDS: Dark fabric structure; Fabriton particles; Dark fabric energy; Travel in a dark fabric

1. INTRODUCTION

Dark fabric matter and the dark energy is an illusion and mystery in the history of a cosmology entirely. Gravity is a tunnel that appeared in a dark fabric matter and energy that pulls inward any neighbour objects into the centre of that tunnel when any celestial objects passed throughout the dark fabric matter, but repulsion force appeared as the gravitational waves when direct interactions occurred between celestial objects and dark fabric matter that pushed on an object to get away from the centre of a tunnel vacuum. The Gravitational Waves may appear during rapid travel of celestial objects in the dark fabric matter are representing the Curvatures and waves that take place in the Dark fabric matter. Most of scientists are believed that the location between stars, planets, galaxies, and visible Universe is an empty, but the reality is that the Universe is filled partially with a dark fabric matter beside an ordinary Matter and Energy. Dark fabric is acting directly on creatures' life and the motion of celestial objects in the visible Universe. It has the ability to attract our body, birds fly, animals, and pushes on you away from place to other places during tunnels and curvatures have been appeared in the dark matter. In past, most People discussed about the dark matter and dark energy, unfortunately they couldn't solve the problem of this hidden matter of the Universe clearly, exactly they couldn't describe its nature in detail. If the location between Sun and Earth being the pure empty, but where the gravitational interaction and combination occurred between both of them, and how solar system and planetary system come to exist in the nature.

The space in the celestial objects and stellar system is not free and absent from matter or another power of nature. The tiny piece of dark fabric matter contained the maximum number of Fabriton particles that had been distributed abundantly inside the structure of the visible Universe and entire Atoms to keep them in balance dynamically and save them in connection tightly and continuously. Atom is filled with subatomic particles and fabriton particles. In fact, atoms, molecules, stellar system, and visible Universe are not free or independent from fabriton particles. Fabriton particle is a cold and dark matter particle. Fabriton particles have been distributed widely in the general structure of entire atoms and Universe, they are building blocks of dark matter and any celestial objects in the nature. There are several models that explained the nature of a dark matter and dark energy of Universe. Solar system is the gravitationally bound system that combined together under an effect of the dark fabric matter and dark energy that distributed in the fabric of a whole solar system, and kept planets orbit the Sun [1]. The dynamical balance between Sun and its entire family kept continuously by the help of dark fabric matter and energy. The solar system may evaporate into space rapidly when dark fabric matter evacuated in its structure. Dark energy accelerated the cosmic expansion and affected on the evolution of a Universe [2]. In Hypersphere world universe model, there was a Fluctuation, but according to the big bang theory of the Universe was a singularity with great density and energy that expanded into space rapidly [3]. The Hypersphere is the World Universe model and the Big Bang

Model are different models of Universe. The value of a dark matter particle mass had been determined by a Yukawa coupling, and Einstein's cosmological constant [4]. Main objectives of this study to explain the general structure of the dark fabric matter, and discuss the evidences of a direct interaction of the dark fabric matter and energy with an ordinary matter and an ordinary energy. The Cosmic Dark fabric matter and dark energy is distributed inside the structure of whole atoms, molecules, materials, planetary system, stellar system, black hole structure, galaxy system, galaxy clusters, Visible Universe, and hold them together gravitationally and dynamically. The total cosmic objects in the visible Universe and entire atoms in the compound materials have been filled with fabriton particles to keep them gravitationally. The celestial objects of Universe will face crises and turbulences with an absent of dark fabric matter and energy. I could recognize new scientific names in this important research for dark matter particles called them fabriton particles, and the best name for the dark matter and the dark energy with a new title named it the dark fabric matter and energy.

2. DARK FABRIC MATTER

Dark fabric matter, or dark matter, is the hidden type of matter that propagates in the body of a whole universe and atoms to keep them balanced statically and dynamically. Actually, the Cosmic Dark Fabric Contains the Dark matter particles and dark Energy. Dark fabric matter and a dark energy could be distorted and vibrates actively under an effect of the total mass and stress of any celestial objects and particles that distributed in the total dimensions of a visible Universe. Black hole has very high density that is why the dark fabric matter was distorted steeply under its mass and pressure [5]. Dark fabric matter existed in the nature as a fabric that named a dark fabric, sometimes named a dark

matter or cosmic dark fabric. Its structure can be classified into Dark matter Particles the fabritons, Dark matter strings, and Dark Webs. Dark fabric structure can be combined in several steps, Firstly, Many Dark matter particles are connecting together in one dimension to make the dark matter strings. Secondly, several dark strings of dark matter were tightened together in two directions to build up dark webs of dark matter. Finally, many dark webs were compacted and combined together in three dimensions to enlarge the size of a dark fabric into all directions. There are many gates, corridors, and vacuums are existed abundantly in the structure and size of a dark fabric matter to let particles and photons pass throughout them easily. Time travel throughout the tunnels and corridors of a dark web is possible. Following explained the general diagram of a dark fabric structure. The tiny point of dark matter or smallest part of dark fabric structure is a dark matter particle that named a Fabriton particle. Fabriton means Fast actively binding reacting in total objects naturally. Fabriton particle is a new name for any dark matter particle or new candidature for the dark matter particle. The nature of a fabriton particle strongly independent and different from the nature of any subatomic particles, and it is a cold, black and dark particle. It may interact with subatomic particles and visible universe to save them cohesively and homogeneously. Subatomic particles are Proton, electron, quarks, and neutrons, they are building blocks of Atoms. Fabriton particle is a building block of dark fabric matter and dark energy. Fabriton particles have been connected and combined together in all directions to build up the general structure of a dark fabric matter and dark energy. The space between electrons and atomic nucleus is filled with a dark fabric matter that kept atoms in a balance and more cohesive. Fig. 1 clearly sketches the general shape and structure of Dark fabric matter and dark matter particles.

Fig. 1. Dark Fabric Structure.

2.1 The Dark Matter Particles

Dark matter Particle is a small point of matter in a dark fabric matter and the dark energy. Mass, radius, density, and energy of dark matter particle are much lower than subatomic particles and higher than photon particles. It is difficult to capture dark matter particles, but its effect clearly founded in the light bending, gravity and gravitational waves. Dark matter particles with unlimited numbers are existed and have been distributed in the vacuum of Universe, the space completed entirely by dark matter particles. Galaxy mostly surrounded by dark matter that acting directly on the formation and bonding of a galaxy disc, the dark matter may reside widely in very large halos and volume around the whole galaxies of visible universe [6]. The theory of dark matter (weakly interacting massive particle) that explains the recent reproduction of observations and technology in astrophysics field [7]. The theory of dark matter particles had been progressed such as weakly interacting of massive particles, such as an axions and sterile neutrinos that has gone widely into direct searching for these particles. The massive experimental efforts around the world and incorporating astronomical surveys among the scientific community, and the gravitational-wave observations and tools are the best targets for making progress on solving the problem of dark-matter particles [8]. Dark Matter Particle looks like dark transparence spheres in its shape. Dark matter particles have been existed in the nature naturally like subatomic particles, the Protons, Electrons, and Neutrons. Dark matter Particles are actively combined together to establish a dark fabric, normally subatomic particles combined together to build up the Atomic Structure. An Imagination of the dark matter

particles in our brain today, Dark matter particles have enough distance and vacuum among them to be vibrated and shifted in their positions to keep objects in balance and bounded. Vacuum and Intermediate Distance Between Dark Matter Particles high enough to let light particles travel easily, the space and intermediate distance existed vastly and may not be big obstacle for an ordinary matter and energy to travel throughout the fabric of dark matter. They like any type of matter and energy interacted with one another through the vacuum that exist among them. Normally every dark particle can occupy special location inside the space according to its size and its mass. The vacuum and distances between dark particles let them to vibrate and move freely in all directions to save general balance of Visible Universe and Atoms. Ordinary matter and ordinary energy directly interacted with dark fabric matter and energy to increase the cohesive and homogeneous of Universe and atoms. Without space and intermediate distance, the dark particles will stay compact and silent in a violent environment. The active vibrations of the dark matter particles referred to a real distance that available among them. All celestial objects and any matter and energy are in motion and vibration continuously because of their particular kinetic energy and intermediate have existed among them and influenced them to gain and lose energy. In fact, the dark matter particles are swimming inside the space of an atom and Universe, and holding them gravitationally. Also, the free vacuum let particles to vibrate and move in all directions without obstacle. The freedom of particles belongs to the vacuum which existed among them. Tiny Distance and corridors among dark matter particles have been sketched clearly in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Dark Matter Particles.

2.1.1 Dark Particles Vibrations and Dark Energy Conversion

Dark matter particle has the ability to move, collide and vibrate, it has enough energy to be vibrated actively in all directions, its vibrations incredibly fast and homogeneous to

transfer dark energy of the Universe. Dark matter particles are vibrating beside one another to exchange an energy among one another when they get excited quickly, they could absorb energy from one another or another sources in the nature. When they got energy directly will begin with fast vibrations

to release an absorbed energy. Nothing stayed silent in the nature, every type of matter, everything in the nature has a power to move and vibrate, anything contains any types of matter and energy exactly has the capacity to vibrate in all directions freely to release absorbed energy. Here the clear figure of dark matter particles when they are vibrating up and down to exchange the Dark Energy between one another. After excitations, dark matter particles will arrive the stable levels, when partially or totally lost their absorbed energy. Dark energy can be converted from one dark matter particle to another directly when they begin with fast vibrations and rapid interactions to release that absorbed energy. Dark energy like any type of energy in the nature can be absorbed and released by dark matter or ordinary matter at same time.

Also, the dark particles same as any other particles in the Universe can be vibrated to exchange dark energy between one another. The dark particles can be vibrated, and waved to convert dark energy among one another to be much stable again and keep the entire balance of a Universe and atoms. Dark matter particles could be created in the nature to connect the celestial objects in the Universe during transferring total gravitational waves in the whole dimensions of a Universe to save the static and dynamical balance of atoms and the visible Universe. Dark matter particles could be vibrated rapidly to transfer dark energy in the structure of atoms and whole Universe. The Dark energy of a whole Universe and atoms could be transferred among dark matter particles as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Dark Particles Vibrations and Dark Energy Conversion.

2.2 Dark Matter Strings

Dark matter strings are tight strings of matter and energy appeared in nature when enough numbers of dark matter particles have been tightly bounded together to build up dark fabric matter. Dark matter string is a second part of dark fabric structure. Dark String consists of several numbers of Dark Matter Particles when interacted and combined together to form it temporary. Dark matter strings contain dark matter particles that vibrate beside one another to exchange an energy directly, without dark matter particles the dark strings can't be formed or appeared in the nature. Many dark matter particles have been vibrated and interacted with one another in all directions to establish the dark fabric strings. The Dark fabric string compacted with one another and expanded in three dimensions to build up the cosmic dark fabric. Following the figure of a dark string. Dark strings like

Mechanical and an Electromagnetic wave have the ability to vibrate and make gravitational waves strongly. When dark matter string absorbed an external energy, it will start with vibrations and waves to transfer an absorbed energy. The absorbed energy can be distributed among dark matter strings to release it entirely. In this method, the energy will be distributed directly among all strings of a dark fabric. Waves in dark matter strings returned to dark particles when got an energy and began actively with vibrations, as a result maximum numbers of particles in much strings of dark fabric will begin with multi vibrations and waves in dark strings step by step. The waves in dark strings like waves in head hairs when affected and vibrated by air molecules. Dark matter strings are squeezing and stretching to transfer dark energy throughout the fabric of cosmos.

Fig. 4. Dark String Wave.

2.3 Dark Matter Webs

Dark matter webs are third branches of a dark fabric structure, and they are formed from an interaction of dark strings with one another. The dark matter particles are combined with one another in two dimensions to build up the dark matter strings. Every dark string contains maximum numbers of dark matter particles when they vibrate beside one another to transfer cosmic energy. In another hand, many dark matter strings have been combined together to establish the dark matter webs. Dark matter webs contain much numbers of compacted and expanded dark matter strings that distributed in three dimensions into space. Dark matter strings combined and tightened together to build up dark matter webs in all directions. Finally, when many dark matter webs were combined together in all directions to produce and develop the body of a cosmic dark fabric in the three dimensions of space. The Dark fabric matter and energy may grow and expand in three dimensions, when enough numbers of the dark matter particles, the dark matter strings, and dark matter webs have been combined and tightened together widely to build up the homogeneous fabric of Universe. The Cosmic dark fabric has been distributed throughout the universe and atoms to protect celestial objects and subatomic particles from collisions and evaporation.

2.3.1 Ripples and Waves in The Dark Matter Webs

Mainly a dark web Structure consists of multi combined cells and tissues that named the dark matter webs. About four strings were tightened together to make a single dark matter web. Furthermore, many dark matter webs successfully contacted together to build the body of a dark fabric matter in a large area of space. The Dark fabric body will grow more and more when many dark matter webs are working together to establish it, as a result a dark matter web will grow more, and it will distribute inside the infinity vacuum. Generally, the dark fabric world is a largest system because many dark matter strings and dark matter webs incredibly combined together and expanded in all dimensions over an open vacuum. Dark matter web like dark matter particles and dark matter strings has the capacity to begin with vibrations and waves. When any web or tiny piece of Dark fabric matter is exposed to any external source of energy or minimum tension directly, it may start with rapid vibrations and waves to transfer that absorbed energy or release it to calm down again. Dark matter webs look like any other dimensions of the Universe, it can be excited when absorbed an external energy, and it can be relaxed when lost an absorbed energy. Many waves clearly can be shown in a dark web structure in the following figure.

Fig. 5. Ripples in the Dark Matter Webs.

2.3.2 Curvatures and Waves in the Dark Matter Webs

Dark Matter web is a soft world, it can be curved and waved vastly when oscillated by any type of matter and an energy during its interaction with any celestial object. When one side of a dark matter web affected by the mass and energy of any external objects directly it will affect other sides to start with vibrations and excitations to release that absorbed energy. The nature of a dark fabric is so strange. It can be expanded and contracted, when an object moved throughout it. Knots in a dark matter web are weak, they may break easily and quickly able to be tightened and arranged again. Knots in a dark matter web can be broken directly, When any matter and energy interact with it or passed throughout it. In another hand, Knots in a dark fabric matter may rebuild again after an effect of an interacting objects on it was ended totally. The binding force among dark matter particles is so weak. Fast broken of a dark matter structure let an object to pass through it easily. When any type of matter and energy was moved throughout a dark matter web, it will bend and shift it actively. When a dark matter web curved under the pressure of an object, it will attract neighbor objects towards the Centre of that object.

If a dark matter web rapidly had been vibrated and waved under the effect of an object, it will push neighbor objects to away from its tunnel center of vibration by an energy carried and transferred during rapid oscillations of dark the dark fabric matter. When a dark matter web exposes to the pressure of any type of matter and energy it will begin

with fast vibrations and expansions in all directions. Dark web is a soft dimension, it can be curved and waved actively under the effect of any objects when they pressed on the dark fabric matter strongly. Normally, dark web can be curved and waved slightly under the effect of radiations. Photon particle has minimum energy to collide directly with a dark fabric matter and able to pass throughout it urgently in the region where the density of a dark matter particles very low, light particles in the place where dark fabric matter not compacted capable travel with a speed same as the speed of the light particles in vacuum. Inside an event horizon zone and around the singularity of a black hole the Light particles will face powerful gravitational wall that obstacle the photons to move slowly in such compacted region of matter and energy, as a result an event horizon of a black hole is a dark and black region of space time. Photon particle will escape from an external edge of a black hole to spread out into space. There are many curvatures and ripples have been occurred in the cosmic dark fabric of matter and energy during its interactions with an ordinary matter and ordinary energy of visible universe to transfer energy. Cosmic energy that named dark energy will transfer throughout the fabric of a Universe as ripples and gravitational waves. Dark fabric matter and energy are distorted violently due to a direct interaction of ordinary matter and energy. The dark fabric matter and energy increased the connection between ordinary matter and celestial objects. We live in an ocean of fabricton particles and gravitational tunnel waves in the fabric of the cosmos.

The Vibration And Expansion Of A Cosmic Dark Web Under The Effect Of A Matter And Energy

Fig. 6. Curvatures and Waves in the Dark Fabric Matter.

3. TUNNELS AND CORRIDORS IN THE DARK FABRIC MATTER

Dark Fabric Matter is a soft fabric contains with multi gates and Tunnels. It can be compressed and expanded warmly under different pressures and stresses from different sources of an ordinary matter and energy. Its density and pressure changeable in different places. When an object with any mass interacted with a dark fabric matter directly, it will make vibrations and expansions in its structure. The binding energy between dark matter particles is not so strong to obstacle the method in front of the motion of an ordinary matter and radiations. Tiny particles like photons and huge body like galaxy clusters able to interact with a dark fabric matter and make tunnels inside its structure easily to be able pass throughout it successfully. The tunnel in a dark web let any objects and photons to move through it very quickly. It is the time travel gate to another world. The Dark web can be curved and waved vastly when ordinary matter and energy contacted with it directly. All kinds of objects may make tunnels in the structure of a dark fabric according to its mass, energy and power. Particles and radiations may build up tiny tunnel in the structure of a dark fabric matter when have been interacted and passed throughout it. Massive, and big size bodies can make large tunnels inside dark fabric according to their masses and Energy. Light is a photon energy can move quickly through dark fabric gates, otherwise the heavy objects, molecules, celestial objects, and atoms are moving slowly through the dark fabric tunnels, because light can pass throughout tiny vacuums, distances, and small tunnels that available in the structure of a dark fabric matter. Atoms and massive objects can move slowly through a dark web because they much needed to make large tunnel inside a dark fabric structure after many interactions with it directly. When any

type of matter and energy moved throughout dark matter structure it may make temporary stretches and compressions in the structure of a dark fabric to build tunnel inside it. An ordinary matter and energy can't pass through dark fabric without making clear tunnels to pass through it. Dark fabric is a great obstacle in the journey of tiny particle such as light, and huge body of the Universe structure such as the Galaxy.

Dark fabric matter and energy curved differently under mass and stress of stars with different masses and density. Dark fabric matter distorted slightly by Low mass stars [9]. The remnant core of a dead solar mass star is a black dwarf star that falls down into the fabric of cosmos deeply. Furthermore, dark fabric matter and energy curved steeply by high mass stars [10]. The remnant core of a high massive star in its final steps of its life will produce a stellar mass black hole that surrounded with an event horizon much larger than a black dwarf star. An ordinary matter with its energy much needed to make enough tunnel and corridor in the dark fabric to travel throughout it. Without tunnels and gates light and ordinary matter can't move throughout space. The space entirely filled with a dark fabric matter and dark fabric energy, the travel from a place to another place needs additional power and energy. Cosmic dark fabric or the dark fabric matter of the universe exists and distributed widely everywhere, and it is being a great obstacle and the largest gravitational wall in our journey to the edge of the Universe. We need additional energy and maximum speed to break that gravitational wall of a dark fabric matter and increase our speed to reach the edge of the visible universe or travel to the outer edge of the solar system in the future. The clear tunnel could be formed in the structure of dark fabric matter when an object passed throughout it as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Tunnel in a Dark Fabric Matter.

4. TRAVEL IN A DARK FABRIC MATTER

Dark Fabric Matter is a soft fabric contains with multi gates, corridors, and Tunnels. Dark Fabric is the hidden bridge and communication dimension of the Universe. The vacuum and among all objects of the visible Universe have been completed by Fabriton particles. Dark fabric has the ability to be compressed, expanded, curved, and waved in all directions. It can be curved and waved actively, when any type of matter and energy travelled through it or interacted with it. Th travel throughout the dark fabric matter and energy much different from place to place. An escape velocity from an external surface of a low- mass and high-mass black holes is same as the speed of light particles, but an escaped velocity from the surface of a black hole singularity much higher than the speed of light, because the density of a black hole singularity incredibly high. The dark fabric matter could be distorted and combined strongly around the singularity sphere that located at the heart of a black hole. For light particle or any other objects to leave the surface of a black hole singularity or fall into it may need the speed much greater than the speed of light, because gravitational field of a black hole singularity much stronger than gravitational field of any celestial objects in the Universe [11]. The dark fabric matter and dark fabric energy incredibly distorted and vibrated by black hole singularity. The direct interactions between dark fabric and visible matter may appear as several curvatures and waves in both of them. The energy can be converted from visible matter and energy into dark fabric matter and dark fabric energy during their direct interactions with one another, the energy could be changed and converted among one another vastly. The conversion energy will support visible matter and energy to pass through

a dark web. Light particle can travel in space freely and easily because little Fabriton particles are distributed in its road, Photon particles will face great absorptions and refractions during its journey inside the black hole, where the dark fabric matter and dark fabric energy have been compressed widely and being much denser than matter in its edge. The black hole singularity is a great regression and distortion region in the whole Universe. Dark matter particles and dark matter strings of a dark web will push an object to move quickly when they interacted and travelled through expanded tunnels in a dark web. Travel in the dark fabric by dark energy is an overexcited travel of an objects throughout a dark fabric, like the travel of a floating objects in the direction of a water waves in rivers, seas, and oceans, the floating body will move quickly in the same directions of water waves. Also, objects, and all types of matter and energy will move quickly with a direction of waves that began in the dark web. The travel in the tunnel of a dark fabric to another world is our dream to fly in the edge of a visible Universe. Dark matter and dark energy will push on you to fly away to deliver another side of the visible Universe. We shall get a benefit from the dark fabric energy to move very quickly into another world at short time. The time travel will be possible soon, when we able to exploit the dark fabric energy successfully.

5. DARK FABRIC ENERGY

Dark fabric energy is the energy quantized in the dark fabric matter, and entire energy of the Universe transferred throughout the fabric of cosmos to save the general dynamical balance of a universe. Dark fabric matter such as any type of an ordinary matter contains enough quantity of matter and

energy to fill the remnant vacuum in the space, it has the ability to vibrate beside one another and push on one another actively to transfer an absorbed energy, and save the stability of a visible Universe. Dark matter particles inside the dark matter web much able to vibrate continuously and release energy. The absolute vacuum of a Universe let dark matter strings to make vibrations and waves vastly. The vacuum between dark matter strings is an important factor for dark matter webs to make vibrations and waves step by step. An ordinary matter and energy of our bright Universe are living and swimming inside vibrated and waved strings of the dark fabric. Actually, dark fabric can be curved and waved under the effects of one another or the stress of other objects of visible matter and energy. The curvatures in a dark web are making the attraction force on the celestial objects when fallen into it, otherwise the waves and vibrations in a dark web represent the repulsion force that push on an object to escape away from the gravity center. The dark web has much power, and energy to attract and repulse massive objects. We must work very hard to detect the top secrets of this hidden dimension of a Universe. As soon as possible this dimension will help us to travel into other side of the Galaxies and Universe. It is hidden power of a Universe; much people are seeking for it, for long time ago. It is between our hands every time; we must exploit it to make miracle for our century and next generations. Today in the dream we are seeing it, and tomorrow will be simple control in our hands to travel by it easily across the large dimensions of the Universe. It will be new fuel for us to travel by it forever. The future of our Universe and everything is related to the dark web's existence. Dark fabric matter and dark energy that called the dark matter and dark energy in the recent publication, or fabricon particles of the dark matter could be distributed in the structure of a visible universe and make it to be combined and contacted gravitationally and participated strongly to transfer an entire energy of any actions in the visible universe and save the general balance of a visible Universe.

6. DARK MATTER AND DARK ENERGY

The history of a dark matter and dark energy so long and full of illusions. Most of people are tried for a long time to describe dark matter, and the dark energy according to their power of understanding about the Universe. Dark matter has been a hot topic in particle physics and astronomy since 1933, when Swiss astronomer Fritz Zwicky confirmed the structure of galaxy and galaxy clusters filled with dark mater, when he observed a discrepancy between the amount of light emitted by a galaxy cluster, and the total amount of mass contained within that cluster of galaxies as inferred from the gravitational behavior of the galaxies within that cluster. In the 1970s and 1980s, the astronomer Vera Rubin observed and detected similar effects in the motion of stars in the galaxy disc. In the past people think the vacuum among objects in the Universe was filled by Ether. Ether a very

rarefied and steeply elastic type of substance scientists thought it may propagate and permeate in the all dimensions of space, including the interstices and empty among the particles of matter, and to be the material medium whose vibrations constituted light particles and other electromagnetic radiation, assuming then that the ether is at rest, the earth moving through it [12]. Dark matter and dark energy dynamic concept were modified vastly the theories of gravity could provide in the future a possible candidate for a dark energy theory that included in the discussion the particle physics and cosmology [13]. The concept of dark matter and dark energy warmly started and developed during theories and experiments by Zwicky's work on dark matter, Riess's findings on dark energy, and recent results from experiments like LUX and LIGO. The story of dark matter and dark energy is still an illusion and mystery in the history of science. My proposal to express a new name for dark matter particles and my massive attempts in the future work to calculate the mass and radius of a fabricon particle will be revolutionary in the future of dark matter and dark energy. The fabricon particle represents the dark matter particle and it is strongly different from subatomic particles and ordinary matter according to its tiny mass and radius. In few years ago, people's understanding deals the Cosmology developed revolutionary. Today, scientists think the vacuum among small and huge bodies in the Universe was completed by Dark Matter and the Dark Energy roughly. Actually, the vacuum is not absolutely freely in the Universe. It is filled partially by dark matter and dark energy. Dark matter and dark energy are a hypothetical form of matter and energy that filled the hidden side of the Universe. The name dark matter and dark energy refers to the fact that it does not appear to interact with observable electromagnetic radiation, such as visible light, as a result it is invisible by naked eyes, also it is dark and cold type of matter and energy as compared to an ordinary matter and energy. Normally, dark matter and energy are invisible (or 'dark') to the entire electromagnetic spectrums, making it extremely difficult to be detected by using normal astronomical equipment, but light is bending and reflected by dark fabric matter and energy. More than 95% the size of an entire Universe is completed by dark matter and dark energy, scientists are believed that the Universe structure contains about 72% the dark energy, and 23% the dark matter, and 5% of the ordinary matter and ordinary energy [14]. Dark matter and dark energy are hidden sides of the Universe, and ordinary matter and ordinary energy are visible dimension of the entire Universe that called a visible Universe. Normally, visible Universe is the much-compacted world of dense subatomic particles that began to deliver into space, and existed during the big bang history, and until today it continuous in the expansion in all directions to complete the space beside the cosmic dark fabric. The Visible universe contains all sorts of matter and energy like, radiations, atoms, meteors, satellites, planets, stars, black holes, and galaxy

clusters. The density and pressure of a visible Universe is higher than the density and pressure of a dark fabric matter and the dark energy because the visible Universe was created from the compacted world during big bang and universe expansions, but the dark matter and energy was existed before the big bang started into existence.

Black hole dark energy radiation theory, and the gravitized vacuum theory are two evidences of how the gravitational force and the gravity might affect as the quantum vacuum [15]. Dark matter has an effect on the entire structure and an evolution of the Universe. The attractive force and the dynamic of an acceleration of the entire Universe expansion caused by an interaction of the dark matter and the dark energy with an ordinary matter [16]. Dark fabric matter and the dark energy are a soft world that filled the vacuum in large volume. It lets visible Universe to live and swim through it easily. It is a soft system like water in the rivers, seas, and oceans can be expanded, waved, and make ripples easily when an object fallen into it. Dark matter and energy are representing the gravitational waves and gravitational lenses. Curvatures in a dark matter and dark energy represent the gravitational lenses. Furthermore, waves in a dark matter and energy represent the gravitational waves. It is the matter and energy that push an object in the space inside a visible Universe. Dark matter and energy can be curved strongly and lightly under the pressure of massive and light objects in the Universe, as a light when passed, curved, and combined throughout gravitational lenses. Also, dark matter and energy can be vibrated by mass and energy to produce the gravitational waves like waves appeared in a water when stone fallen into it or an object passed throughout the water. Dark fabric matter and energy is a new understanding to the dark matter and energy. The properties of a dark fabric can be classified here warmly. The dark fabric matter and dark energy is the modern idea deals the gravity and gravitational waves. The curvatures and waves that happened in the dark fabric structures are two important factors for an object's motions in the nature. Dark fabric is the natural power, and the mechanism of entire actions and events that occurred in the total structure of a visible Universe and atoms. Stars and galaxies are holding together gravitationally by dark fabric matter and energy. Nucleus of atom and electrons are holding together by electromagnetic force and dark fabric matter and energy that completed the free space among electrons and atomic nuclei.

7. GRAVITATIONAL THEORIES

The story of gravity was started warmly by Newton and Einstein. Unfortunately, both of Newton and Einstein have only pure mathematical description to Gravity and gravitational effects. Curvatures and tunnels that occurred in the structure of a dark fabric matter and energy during its direct interaction with an ordinary matter and energy, and celestial objects is a new candidate of gravity and

gravitational waves. Newton is one of the famous scientists in the era of Classical Physics, he explained the roots of gravity and the gravitational at his time by using mathematical equations. Newton has his own the famous equation in the gravity and gravitational force. Formulating the Newton's theory of a gravity and the gravitational force is as the theory of a gravitational field in a background of the spacetime that given as a curved spacetime formulation by geometricizing the gravitational fields, gravitational force, and incorporating it into the curvature tensors in general relativity [17]. Newton's law of the gravitation arises in a much complex theories of the gravity in which space time emerges through a holographic scenario model [18]. For two bodies having different masses m and M with a clear distance r between their centers of masses, the equation for the Newton's Universal equation of a gravitational force is written as:

$$F = G \frac{M \cdot m}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

Where F is symbolized the gravitational force, and G is the gravitational constant and it has been measured experimentally to be:

$$G = 6.67410^{-11} \frac{N \cdot m^2}{Kg^2}$$

Einstein was published Special relativity theory and general relativity theory in a Physics. Einstein's principle of equivalence implies that light will redshift and dissipate in a gravitational field [19]. The effect of a vacuum between objects in the Universe was described by Einstein as the Space and the Time Curvatures. He could write his own famous equation deals the space time curvature of the universe that called an Einstein's Field Equation (EFE). The gravitational field equations of the universe are derived based only on the Einstein's principle of the general relativity theory, and the principle of the interaction dynamics, due to the presence and clear effects of the dark energy and the dark matter that reflect the role of gravitational waves and gravitational energy [20]. The Einstein field equation (EFE) could be written Mathematically in the following form:

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} + R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{C^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (2)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci curvature tensors, R is the scalar curvatures, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, Λ is the cosmological constant of the universe, Normally G is the gravitational constant, c is the speed of light particles and the electromagnetic radiations in the vacuum, and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress – energy tensor. The EFE is a tensor equation relating a set of symmetric 4×4 tensors. Each tensor has 10 independent components. The mystery of a gravity still under review and revision by scientists and cosmologists. This mystery could not be solved by ancient scientists and even recent time it is

big illusion and needed to much work to increase our comprehension of gravity and build up new concepts and do many experiments to understand this illusion scientifically and experimentally. The physics of black hole and gravitational waves expanded from Einstein’s predictions in the relativity theory [21]. The relativity is a main theory of the gravity, gravitational waves, black holes, and the black hole singularity. Gravitational theories have been developed widely and abundantly to explain the reality of gravity and its mechanism. Cosmic fabric theory or Atomic fabric theory of gravity that called Fabric Theory or gravitational tunnel waves theory is a good candidate for the whole theory of gravity, universe and atom.

8. FORMATION AND ANNIHILATION OF THE TUNNELS IN THE COSMIC DARK FABRIC

Dark fabric matter is unstable dimension of a Universe and atom, vibrations and curvatures produced in its structure continuously when it was exposed to any amount of stress and energy from celestial objects. Actually, the dark fabric structure is not compacted 100%. It has the vacuum between its particles, strings, and dark matter webs. The absolute space between dark web structure let the dark web to vibrate and move freely. The vacuum is infinity dimension of the existence. The dark web matter and energy is only tiny system that filled the absolute vacuum partially, and another fraction of the space partially was completed by ordinary matter of visible Universe in the other side of space. The absolute vacuum is a full freedom for the swimming of a dark matter particles and subatomic particles. An ordinary matter and energy are more massive and powerful than dark matter and dark energy. They are getting vibrations and interactions together continuously inside the absolute space. Dark web can be separated and expanded under the effect of an object of a visible Universe. Visible or ordinary matter and energy are normal matter and energy that created our body and total visible Universe. The parallel universes, visible universe, celestial objects, atoms, and our body could be formed by ordinary matter, and dark matter particles that called fabriton particles. The concept of dark matter has been present since the 1930s as Zwicky has postulated the existence of unseen dark matter invisible matter. Nearly seven decades later, the idea of dark energy emerged by Riess with his colleagues. Over time, numerous theories, experiments, and hypotheses have been formulated to elucidate the enigma of dark matter and dark energy, yet a definitive and straight-forward solution remains elusive and great mystery in the history of science and cosmology. I have worked hard to find new and suitable name for a dark matter particle. I have called it a fabriton particle according to its nature its fast and active interactions with ordinary matter and ordinary objects and its abundance in the structure of total celestial objects to keep them in contact and cohesive continuously. The visible universe and atoms may evaporate entirely with an absence of fabriton

particles. Weakly Interacting Massive Particles (WIMPs), represent one hypothesized class of particles to explain dark matter particles. According to this model, dark matter neither absorbs nor emits light particles and doesn't interact strongly with other particles or atoms. The fabriton particles are dark matter particles abundantly propagated in the vacuum of atoms, and celestial objects and interact strongly or weakly with photon particles. The photons are absorbed and reflected steeply around the edge of a black hole where fabriton particles had been distorted strongly around the surface of a black hole singularity. The photon particles can travel easily among fabriton particles in space and on the edge of celestial objects where their fabriton particle are slightly distorted and curved around Earth and stars. The mass and radius of a fabriton particle are approximately lower than the mass and radius of any subatomic particles, and the wavelength of photon particles could be larger than the diameter of fabriton particles, the density of fabriton particles is incredibly low in the edge of stars and planets, the light bending and reflections may be very low in the region where the density of dark matter particles reduced, number of fabriton particles here very poor as a result the interaction of fabriton particles with light in such environment lower than the edge of black holes. The photon particles steeply trapped and dissipated urgently in the compacted fabric of dark matter that curved and turbulent around the squeezed singularity of a black hole. The visible Universe contains 5 % of ordinary matter and energy. The density and energy of normal matter and energy are higher than that of dark matter and energy.

When any objects with any quantity of matter and energy directly interacted with a dark fabric matter, it will make separations, and distortions in the dark web structure, and may build up the gates and tunnels in its structure instantly. Black hole singularity and black hole itself will move throughout the dark fabric matter, and able to make tunnels in structure of dark fabric matter [22]. Tunnel could be formed in the dark fabric matter when any celestial object passed throughout it directly, but the tunnel could be annihilated when celestial object passed away entirely from such created tunnel. Tunnels are produced and annihilated after an object with any mass and energy interacted with a dark fabric matter. Gravitational attraction and repulsion forces are clear evidences of the formation and annihilation of such tunnels in the fabric of cosmos. Actually, the combination force between dark matter particles is so weak, as a result visible matter and energy can interact with a dark web and able to make the tunnel throughout its path and journey. The dark fabric matter is a future fuel and the time gate to another world. We may use the matter and energy of dark fabric as fuel to travel by it into the edge of galaxies and visible universe by future time machine. It is an infinity power of the nature.

When celestial objects, visible matter and energy interacted with a dark fabric matter, and built up the tunnel in

its structure it may return to its original stable state when an effect of celestial object on the formation of such tunnels have been dissipated. The dark fabric particles may combine together directly after the effect of a visible objects ended on it. The dark web structure has the capacity to separate from one another under particular pressure of massive objects, also it has the ability to combine together again after the effect of celestial objects vanished on it totally. When any type of matter and energy passed through dark web, it will make the separations, ripples, and curvatures in its structure. When an object passed through the part of a dark web successfully, the dark web will combine together again to complete the separations, and vacuums that occurred in the dark fabric. The free position of a dark web tunnel can be filled with dark web particles again when the effect of that object ended on the dark web totally. The name of a dark web come from its property. It is dark because cannot be seen by naked eyes, it cannot emit light energy, and it has the ability to separate from one another under the effect of an objects, and it has the capacity to recombine itself together again when the effect of an object was finished on it totally. It is an active dimension in the nature. It is actively interacting with everything in the nature. The curvatures, waves, gates, and Tunnels in a dark web can be created continuously when an ordinary matter and

energy interacted directly with a dark web as shown as following figure. The tunnels and gates that formed in the cosmic dark fabric let celestial objects to pass throughout it easily. Separation and Combination properties of a Dark Fabric Matter let the dark fabric to be soft dimension of the Universe. Celestial objects may make tunnels in the dark fabric that attract nearby objects to fall down into that tunnel, otherwise gravitational waves that formed from direct interactions between celestial objects and dark fabric matter may repulse objects actively to get away from the throat of that tunnel. Tunnels are formed temporary in the dark fabric matter, and annihilated after external effect of the celestial objects was removed on it permanently. The use of MATLAB for better and more concise graphing is commendable. Dark fabric matter and the dark fabric energy roughly represented the space matter and gravitational force according to eq. (3), and the MATLAB program is used to draw the shape of gravity, attraction force, and repulsion forces as the tunnels, gravitational waves, and dark fabric distortions in three dimensions (x,y,z) that appeared clearly in the structure of a dark fabric matter under the stress of mass and energy from an ordinary matter and energy that passed through the dark fabric matter as shown here in a fig.(8):

$$z = \frac{1}{\cosh(x^2+y^2)} - \frac{\coth(x^2+y^2)}{\tan(x^2+y^2)} \tag{3}$$

Suppose: $-\frac{\pi}{2} < x < \frac{\pi}{2}$, $-\frac{\pi}{2} < y < \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Fig. 8. Formation and Annihilation of the Tunnels in a Dark Fabric Matter

9. GRAVITATIONAL TUNNEL WAVES

Gravitational tunnel wave is a recent strong candidate to solve the illusion of gravity and gravitational waves entirely. Gravitational tunnel waves are temporary tunnels and ripples have been occurred in the body of a dark fabric matter and energy when celestial objects and subatomic particles are passed in the dark fabric matter. Gravitational

tunnel waves appeared in dark fabric matter due to the continuous motions and rapid vibrations of cosmic objects and subatomic particles, which saved the entire universe and atoms from evaporation and carried the energy of their vibrations. Gravitational tunnels in the dark fabric matter may attract celestial objects towards the center of a tunnel vacuum, the ripples and gravitational waves that formed from rapid

transition of celestial objects in the tunnel of dark fabric matter may repulse nearby objects to get way from mouth of gravitational tunnel. Both of gravitational tunnel and gravitational waves that produced during a rapid transition of a celestial object in the structure of a cosmic dark fabric named gravitational tunnel waves. The planet Earth is celestial object is traveling in the dark fabric matter and making up tunnel and gravitational waves in the dark fabric matter, and acting directly on the attraction and repulsion its natural satellite the Lunar. Earth is a planet that moving with a speed 30 kilometers per second and making gravitational tunnel waves in the dark fabric matter as tornado eye to attract and repulse celestial objects and holding its atmosphere from its surrounding. Gravitational tunnel waves that produced by rapid motion of Earth inside a cosmic dark fabric helped living creatures on the Earth and gaseous molecules in the atmosphere to be stable and cohesive gravitationally with a surface of Earth planet, and let objects to fall down freely into the center of Earth.

10. CONCLUSION

In this research, dark fabric matter structure can be classified into three parts as dark matter particles that called fabriton particles, dark matter strings, and the dark matter webs. Dark fabric matter and dark fabric energy can be curved and oscillated in all directions when ordinary matter and energy interacted with it. Visible matter and energy of our Universe may interact with a dark fabric matter and passed throughout it easily. Dark fabric like the ocean water, all types of matter and energy are living and swimming inside it continuously, without a dark fabric matter, small and huge objects in the Universe will lose connections with one another. Actually, the dark fabric matter is existed here to complete the free vacuum of Universe and hold the total objects in the Universe gravitationally. Cosmic Dark Fabric contains the dark matter and the dark energy that acting strongly on the acceleration and deceleration of the cosmic objects. Tunnels and gravitational waves could be occurred in the Dark fabric matter when any celestial objects and subatomic particles are passed throughout it. The mysterious of a dark matter and dark energy can be solved here clearly. Unfortunately, both of Einstein and Newton or any other scientists still couldn't describe the structure of dark fabric matter and energy, and lost the chance to solve the gravitational effects clearly. Fortunately, after deep thinking and hardworking during long time ago, I could describe the general structure of a dark fabric matter and energy, its effects and its interactions with our visible Universe, and eventually solved the mysterious of a gravity, dark matter and dark energy with my humble. First and final candidate of gravity and repulsion force are the gravitational tunnel waves that appeared in the structure of a dark fabric matter and energy as the tunnels and ripples that attract, and repulse celestial objects, and hold entire celestial objects, and atoms in a

perfect balance and cohesive naturally. Gravitational tunnel waves model is a new professional candidature for the theory of gravity and quantum mechanics. Gravitational tunnel waves occurred due to the transition of any tiny and big objects in the universe to transfer energy and save entire structure of universe from evaporations.

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CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

I have used advanced mathematical equations and MATLAB program to figure out an interaction of the celestial objects and ordinary matter particles with dark fabric matter and energy.

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